

Myth 3: Preprints are not discoverable or citable

YouTube Description Box

Myth: “Preprints are not discoverable or citable.”

Truth: Preprints are an established part of today’s research ecosystem—they have DOIs, appear in major databases, and are recognized by both journals and funders.

In this episode of **the ASAPbio Myth Busting Series**, we unpack how preprints are indexed, cited, and used across the scientific community. Many reference databases now include preprints; most journals explicitly allow citing them; and funders accept them as evidence of research productivity. Sometimes, preprints can serve as the “director’s cut” of a paper, containing more detail than the final published version and making it the best source to cite.

✨ **Takeaway:** Preprints are discoverable, citable, and reshaping how we communicate science.

📖 Selected References:

- Levchenko M, Parkin M, McEntyre J, Harrison M. 2024. Enabling preprint discovery, evaluation, and analysis with Europe PMC. PLoS One 19:e0303005. doi:10.1371/journal.pone.0303005
- Klebel T, Reichmann S, Polka J, McDowell G, Penfold N, Hindle S, Ross-Hellauer T. 2020. Peer review and preprint policies are unclear at most major journals. PLoS One 15:e0239518. doi:10.1371/journal.pone.0239518
- Fraser N, Momeni F, Mayr P, Peters I. 2020. The relationship between bioRxiv preprints, citations and altmetrics. Quant Sci Stud 1–21. doi:10.1162/qss_a_00043
- Colavizza G, Cadwallader L, Hrynaszkiewicz I. 2025. An analysis of the effects of open science indicators on citations in the French Open Science Monitor. arXiv [csDL]. doi:10.48550/arXiv.2508.20747

See Zenodo (linked below) for the full reference list.

🔗 Zenodo link: doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17154631

🌐 Learn more at <https://asapbio.org>

🔔 Don’t forget to like, comment, and subscribe for more myth-busting insights about preprints and open science!

Script

Camera 1-2

Welcome to the ASAPbio Myth Busting Series.

Have you ever heard someone say, “Preprints are not discoverable or citable?” That sounds like a big problem – but is it true? Let’s take a closer look.

Camera 3-4

Preprints receive DOIs, or Digital Object Identifiers. The DOI is a unique and persistent identifier that makes digital resources easy to find and cite. Thanks to DOIs, preprints are discoverable in systems like Google Scholar and Crossref, just like journal articles.

On top of that, many reference databases also index preprints. The exact scope depends on their selection criteria.

- For instance, the Web of Science Preprint Citation Index contains 2.5 million preprints from 5 major repositories: arXiv, bioRxiv, medRxiv, chemRxiv, and preprints.org.¹
- PubMed, through the NIH Preprint Pilot, indexes all preprints from arXiv, bioRxiv, medRxiv, and Research Square published after 2023 and acknowledging NIH support.²
- And Europe PMC now links to preprints from more than 30 servers.^{3,4}

Far from being hidden, preprints are woven into the same literature discovery infrastructure that researchers use every day.

Camera 5A

Now, discoverability only matters if we can also cite preprints. So are preprints citable? The answer is a clear **yes**.

Most journals explicitly allow citations to preprints⁵ – including top names like Nature⁶, Science⁷, and PNAS⁸. In fact, journal author guidelines often spell this out directly.

¹ Preprint Citation Index. 2025. Web of Science. [Accessed 19 Oct 2025]. <https://webofscience.zendesk.com/hc/en-us/articles/31149528467089-Preprint-Citation-Index>

² NIH Preprint Pilot. 2025. . PubMed Central (PMC). [Accessed 19 Oct 2025]. <https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/about/nihpreprints/>

³ Preprints in Europe PMC. n.d. . [Accessed 19 Oct 2025]. Europe PMC. <https://europepmc.org/Preprints>

⁴ Levchenko M, Parkin M, McEntyre J, Harrison M. 2024. Enabling preprint discovery, evaluation, and analysis with Europe PMC. PLoS One 19:e0303005. doi:10.1371/journal.pone.0303005

⁵ Klebel T, Reichmann S, Polka J, McDowell G, Penfold N, Hindle S, Ross-Hellauer T. 2020. Peer review and preprint policies are unclear at most major journals. PLoS One 15:e0239518. doi:10.1371/journal.pone.0239518

⁶ Formatting guide. n.d. . Springer Nature. [Accessed 19 Oct 2025]. <https://www.nature.com/nature/for-authors/formatting-guide>

⁷ Instructions for preparing an initial manuscript. n.d. . Science. [Accessed 19 Oct 2025]. <https://www.science.org/content/page/instructions-preparing-initial-manuscript>

⁸ Submitting Your Manuscript. n.d. . PNAS. [Accessed 19 Oct 2025]. <https://www.pnas.org/author-center/submitting-your-manuscript>

And funders? They are on board, too. The NIH⁹, Wellcome¹⁰, and Gates Foundation¹¹ encourage researchers to list preprints in grant applications and progress reports as evidence of productivity.

Camera 5B

And this isn't just policy on paper—preprints are **already** being cited across peer-reviewed articles, policy documents, and even mainstream news coverage.¹²

Large-scale studies show that preprints are not only citable, they're actively cited—often before the journal version of record appears.⁹ Recent analyses even suggest a citation boost—roughly 20% increase in citation counts for works first posted as a preprint.¹³ So, in practice, researchers are already treating preprints as a normal part of the scholarly record.

Camera 6

Here is something that may not be immediately apparent: a preprint can contain more details than the final published paper.

Why? Journals often impose word counts, figure limits, or formatting requirements. That means extended methods, additional data, or longer discussions are sometimes only present in the preprint.

Think of preprint as the director's cut of the research—the full version before the editing begins. In cases like this, citing the preprint isn't only acceptable – it may be the best way to point readers to the complete story.

⁹ NOT-OD-17-050: Reporting Preprints and Other Interim Research Products. 2017. NIH. <https://grants.nih.gov/grants/guide/notice-files/not-od-17-050.html>

¹⁰ Complying with our open access policy. n.d. . Wellcome. [Accessed 19 Oct 2025] <https://wellcome.org/research-funding/guidance/open-access-guidance/complying-with-our-open-access-policy>

¹¹ 2025 Open Access Policy. 2024. Gates Foundation. [Accessed 19 Oct 2025] <https://openaccess.gatesfoundation.org/open-access-policy/2025-open-access-policy/>

¹² Fraser N, Momeni F, Mayr P, Peters I. 2020. The relationship between bioRxiv preprints, citations and altmetrics. *Quant Sci Stud* 1–21. doi:10.1162/qss_a_00043

¹³ Colavizza G, Cadwallader L, Hrynaszkiewicz I. 2025. An analysis of the effects of open science indicators on citations in the French Open Science Monitor. *arXiv [csDL]*. doi:10.48550/arXiv.2508.20747

Camera 7

So let's go back to our myth: Are preprints **not** discoverable or citable?

The reality is clear:

- Preprints are discoverable through DOIs and indexed in reference databases
- Journals and funders recognize them as legitimate scholarly outputs
- Preprints are being cited—in huge numbers and in different settings
- And sometimes, the preprint is the more complete version of the work

Preprints are not only discoverable and citable—they are reshaping how we communicate science.

Camera 8

Thank you for tuning in! This video was created and produced by ASAPbio. If you found it helpful, please like, comment, and subscribe. For more insights, check out the video description box for references and resources. And don't forget to visit the ASAPbio website or follow us across all of the social media!